

The Use of e-Textbook in the Higher Education: Literature Review

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Abstract - Today, digitalization of the educational process is an effective way to improve the quality of education. The electronic textbook is used as a main tool to improve the digitalization of the education process. We know that the electronic textbook is created with the aim of expanding the presentation, development and deepening of existing knowledge, provides access to additional information for students and is designed to provide in-depth study of the discipline. In this paper, we briefly discuss the literature that are devoted to the development and use of electronic learning tools.

Key words: education, multimedia tools, electronic textbook

I. INTRODUCTION

In the past, the information delivered on the printed materials like book, magazine and newspaper now come via computer, television, radio or video. Especially, computers and internet facilitate too much producing, spreading and using of information. This situation makes most of people direct to computers instead of books and brings obtaining of new information from screens. Therefore, there is a new reading type which is called 'reading on the screen' [3]. Today, e-books are gaining great popularity. A number of foreign scientists (Doering, Torsten & Pereira, Luiz & Kuechler, Linda) determined that e-book sales broke records in 2010, increasing by 164.4 percent, reaching \$441.3 million and accounting for 8.32% of the e-book market. Amazon reported that for its top 10 best-selling physical books, customers bought a Kindle edition twice as often as a hard copy. Kindle e-book sales also surpassed hardcover and paperback print sales in the top 25, Top 100, and top 1000 bestsellers [2]. In this paper, we briefly discuss the literature that are devoted to the development and use of electronic learning tools.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The analysis of the literature shows that the development and use of electronic learning tools developed in two main directions. Within the framework of the first direction, automated training systems for various academic disciplines are being developed and operated. The core of automated training systems are the so-called author systems that allow teachers to enter their educational and methodological material into a database and program algorithms for its study using specialized tools.

According to the Uzbek researcher (A. Khodzhiyev) the electronic textbook is the main educational electronic publication created at a high scientific and methodological level, fully corresponding to the component of the discipline

of the educational standard of specialties and directions determined by the didactic units of the standard and the program, ensuring the continuity and completeness of the didactic cycle of the learning process, subject to interactive feedback [3]. Based on the above, let us turn to the opinion of foreign scientists (Kuo-Liang Huang, Kuo-Hsiang Chen) who believe that due to a more nonlinear experience, teachers realized that they would need to create a "toolkit", not a "textbook", and provide students with several ways to navigate through thematic areas [4].

According to Kazakh researcher (Tortayeva A.K.) an electronic textbook is a methodological complex designed to study the course of the material. It is an integrated tool containing theory, practice, tasks and other components [5]. Based on the above proposals, the electronic textbook is considered as a training software tool [6]. Olsen et al. [7] conducted a research project at one of universities in Norway that investigated the use of e-readers during the education process. The authors conducted a survey among 94 students on the use of two popular e-reader technologies, such as Kindle DX and iPad. The result of their survey demonstrated that the students were generally positive to use the electronic versions of educational materials. On the other hand, iPad overwhelmingly preferred education tool by the students mainly because it enables students take a notes on the e-Textbooks.

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